

CAUSES, TYPES AND COMPLICATIONS OF UTERINE MYOMA.

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Uterine fibroids are a diagnosis that scares every woman. Such a decision of an ultrasound diagnostic doctor can make even the most resilient women panic. However, you should not suddenly worry about the risk of fibroids. First, during the next menstrual cycle, it is necessary to contact another specialist and repeat the ultrasound examination (UZI). What is uterine myoma, why does it appear, myoma treatment with conservative and surgical methods and what are its symptoms? Let's talk about it in detail. Uterine myoma is a harmless tumor originating from smooth muscles.

Fibroids often cause abnormal uterine bleeding, pelvic pain and pelvic organ compression, dysuric disorders, bowel dysfunction, and difficulties during pregnancy. Diagnosis is made using ultrasound and pelvic examination or other diagnostic visual imaging techniques. Treatment of symptomatic patients depends on the patient's ability to become pregnant and the desire to preserve the uterus. Treatment may include oral contraceptives, short-term preoperative gonadotropin-releasing hormone therapy to shrink the fibroid, progestin therapy, and more radical surgical procedures (eg, hysterectomy, myomectomy). Uterine fibroids are the most common pelvic tumors. It occurs in about 70% of patients under the age of 45. At the same time, myoma is often asymptomatic and has a small size. About 25% of white men and 50% of black women eventually develop symptomatic fibroids. Uterine fibroids are more common in women with a high body mass index. Potential factors include pregnancy and cigarette smoking.

Causes of uterine myoma

Often, the development of uterine fibroids is associated with hormonal disorders in women, especially with an increase in the concentration of estrogen. This hormonal disorder is more typical for young women in the reproductive period. Due to the natural decrease of estrogen hormones during menopause, uterine fibroids may disappear on their own, regardless of treatment. In addition, the causes of uterine fibroids may include:

Hereditary predisposition;

- Hormonal disorders;
- Adenomyosis;
- Inflammatory process in the genitals;
- Metabolic diseases (including diabetes);

- Chronic systemic diseases;
- Sedentary lifestyle, overweight;
- Chronic stress;
- Effects of abortion, use of intrauterine contraceptives;
- Dissatisfaction with sexual life (sexual anorgasmia).

The following types of uterine fibroids are most common:

- Subserous (most common)
- Intramural
- Submucosal (rare)

Also, nodes can be in the wide joints of the uterus (intraligamentary or inter-articular), fallopian tubes or cervix.

Pedunculate fibroids are also found. Most fibroids consist of several parts. Each of them develops from a single smooth muscle cell, which means that they are of monoclonal origin. Because they affect estrogen, fibroids increase during the reproductive period and decrease after menopause. Fibroids can outgrow the blood supply; in such cases, their decline begins. Myoma can have hyaline, myxomatous, calcified, cystic, fatty, red or necrotic degeneration areas. Although patients are often concerned about cancer in fibroids, sarcomatous changes occur in <1% of patients.

Complications of Uterine Fibroids Fibroids can cause abnormal uterine bleeding (eg, menorrhagia, menometrorrhagia). If a fibroid grows and degenerates, or a pedunculated fibroid twists, it can cause severe or chronic pressure and pain. Urinary symptoms (such as bothersome or frequent urination) can be caused by bladder compression, and bowel symptoms (such as constipation) can be caused by bowel compression.

Fibroids can increase the risk of infertility. During pregnancy, they can cause repeated miscarriages, premature contractions or abnormal fetal appearance, or require a caesarean section. Fibroids can also cause postpartum hemorrhage.

